

1 **Global burden of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease attributable to ambient**
2 **particulate matter pollution and household air pollution from solid fuels from 1990**
3 **to 2019**

4

5 Yinglin Wu ^a, Shiyu Zhang ^a, Bingting Zhuo ^a, Miao Cai ^a, Zhengmin (Min) Qian ^b, Michael G. Vaughn
6 ^c, Stephen Edward McMillin ^c, Zilong Zhang ^{a,*}, Hualiang Lin ^{a,*}

7

8 **Affiliations:**

9 ^a Department of Epidemiology, School of Public Health, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China

10 ^b Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, College for Public Health & Social Justice, Saint Louis
11 University, Saint Louis, MO, USA

12 ^c School of Social Work, College for Public Health & Social Justice, Saint Louis University, Saint Louis,
13 MO, USA

14

15 * Correspondence authors:

16 Zilong Zhang, PhD

17 Department of Epidemiology, School of Public Health, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China; E-
18 mail: zhangzilong@mail.sysu.edu.cn; Address: #74 Zhongshan Road 2, Yuexiu District, Guangzhou
19 510080, China

20

21 Hualiang Lin, PhD

22 Department of Epidemiology, School of Public Health, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China; E-
23 mail: linhualiang@mail.sysu.edu.cn; Address: #74 Zhongshan Road 2, Yuexiu District, Guangzhou
24 510080, China

25

26 **Abstract**

27 We aimed to estimate the spatiotemporal trends in the global burden of chronic obstructive pulmonary
28 disease (COPD) attributable to both household air pollution from solid fuels (HAP) and ambient
29 particulate matter (APM) from 1990 to 2019 and compared the possible differences between the
30 burdens attributable to APM and HAP. The number of deaths, disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs)
31 and years of life lost (YLLs) of COPD attributable to HAP from solid fuels and APM during 1990-
32 2019 were extracted from the Global Burden of Diseases Study 2019. The proportion of YLLs in
33 DALYs and average YLLs per COPD death were also calculated. Subgroup analyses by sex, age, and
34 socio-demographic index (SDI) were conducted. The estimated annual percentage change (EAPC) was
35 used to assess the temporal trend of age-standardized rate of mortality (ASMR) and DALYs (ASDR).
36 Over the past 30 years, we observed a clear downward trend in COPD deaths attributable to HAP and
37 an upward trend by 97.61% in COPD deaths attributable to APM. The global COPD burden
38 attributable to APM in 2019 was higher than those due to HAP, except in low-SDI regions. For both
39 HAP and APM, YLLs continued to predominate in DALYs of COPD, with an average YLLs per
40 death of more than 10 years in different regions. The ASMR was higher in males and lower in high-
41 SDI regions. The ASMR and ASDR attributable to HAP decreased globally in all age groups during
42 1990-2019, while those attributable to APM increased among people older than 80 years and in regions
43 with lower SDI. Our study reveals an increasing trend in APM-attributable COPD burden over the past
44 three decades. Comparatively, the global burden due to HAP decreased markedly, but it was still
45 pronounced in low-SDI regions. Continued efforts on PM mitigation are needed for COPD prevention.

46

47 **Keywords:** Particulate matter; chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; global burden of disease;
48 mortality; disability-adjusted life years

49

50 **1. Introduction**

51 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) poses a threat to global health, with an estimated
52 prevalence of approximately 300 million in 2017 (GBD Chronic Respiratory Disease Collaborators
53 2020). It is also a leading cause of mortality and disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) globally (GBD
54 2019 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators 2020), accounting for 3.20 million deaths and 81.60 million
55 DALYs in 2017 (Li et al. 2020). The etiology of COPD is complicated and involves multiple factors
56 such as genetics, lifestyle and environmental exposures (Ni et al. 2020, Sadhra et al. 2020,
57 Singanayagam & Johnston 2020, Tian et al. 2020). Compelling epidemiologic studies suggested that
58 particulate matter (PM) air pollution is an important environmental risk factor for COPD (Cao et al.
59 2021, Li et al. 2016, Park et al. 2021).

60 The source of PM includes ambient PM pollution (APM) mainly originating from transportation
61 and power plants, and household air pollution from combustion of solid fuels (HAP) (GBD 2019 Risk
62 Factors Collaborators 2020). Long-term exposure to PM pollution, especially PM with an aerodynamic
63 diameter smaller than or equal to $2.5\mu\text{m}$ ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$), may transport deep into the lung and trigger oxidative
64 stress and inflammatory responses, leading to chronic respiratory inflammation and fibrosis (Liu et al.
65 2017, Niu et al. 2021, Xia et al. 2020).

66 However, previous studies have focused on the effects of APM and HAP on COPD and their
67 potential mechanism, usually in a certain region or at a specific time, and no studies have
68 systematically assessed the trend of the population attributable burden over the past 30 years from a
69 global perspective. Furthermore, the majority of previous studies only assessed morbidity and mortality
70 attributable to either APM or HAP, and a comparison is needed to explore the possible differences
71 between APM and HAP. Therefore, we conducted this study to estimate the spatiotemporal trends of
72 global burden of COPD attributable to both HAP and APM from 1990 to 2019 using data from the
73 Global Burden of Disease study (GBD) 2019. Given the scope of the present study, our findings would
74 help to inform the development of more effective strategies to reduce PM-associated COPD burden.

75

76 **2. Methods**

77 *2.1 Data sources*

78 We retrieved the relevant data on the burden of COPD attributable to PM air pollution from the GBD

79 2019 through the Global Health Data Results Tool (GHDx, <http://ghdx.healthdata.org/gbd-results-tool>).
80 The GBD 2019 comprehensively estimated the mortality and disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs) of
81 369 diseases and injuries for 204 countries and territories from 1990 to 2019, using a unified and
82 comparable approach. Details of this study have been described elsewhere (GBD 2019 Risk Factors
83 Collaborators 2020). Four indicators of COPD disease burden attributable to APM and HAP were used
84 in the present study, including mortality, DALYs, years of life lost (YLLs) and years lived with
85 disability (YLDs).

86 In the GBD 2019, countries and territories were divided into 21 regions according to
87 epidemiological and geographical characteristics (GBD 2019 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators
88 2020). Their locations are illustrated in Figure S1. We also classified countries and territories into
89 different regions based on SDI, which was a comprehensive indicator of average year of education,
90 total fertility rate (TFR), and the lag-distributed income per capita in a country (GBD 2019
91 Demographics Collaborators 2020, GBD 2019 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators 2020).

92

93 *2.2 Assessment of PM air pollution exposure*

94 HAP in the GBD 2019 was defined as the HAP from household combustion of solid fuels, and the
95 estimation methods have been described in detail elsewhere (GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators
96 2020). Briefly, it was estimated from both the proportion of individuals using solid fuels and the level
97 of excess PM_{2.5} exposure for these individuals. Solid fuels included coal, wood, charcoal, dung, and
98 agricultural residues such as crop stalks, husks, or straw. The GBD 2019 synthesized the household
99 solid fuels use data from a variety of standard multi-country surveys that surveyed the household
100 information, such as Demographic and Health Surveys, Living Standards Measurement Surveys,
101 Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys, and World Health Surveys (GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators
102 2020). The proportion of PM exposure from solid fuels at the individual level was then modelled using
103 linear, spatiotemporal, and Gaussian regression three-step modelling strategy. The individual excess
104 PM exposure due to using solid fuels was estimated by a linear model using the study database from
105 the Global Household Air Pollution measurement database from WHO (Shupler et al. 2018a). The level
106 of HAP exposure due to combustion of solid fuels was then estimated using a Bayesian, hierarchical
107 model based on the excess HAP data aforementioned (GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators 2020,

108 Shupler et al. 2018b).

109 APM exposure in the GBD 2019 study was defined as the population-weighted annual average
110 concentration of PM_{2.5} (µg/m³), which was estimated by multiple sources using ground measurements,
111 satellite observations, chemical transport model simulations, population estimates, and land-use data.
112 The estimation approach has been previously detailed (GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators 2020). In
113 brief, the PM_{2.5} ground measurement database consisted of updated data from the WHO Global
114 Ambient Air Quality Database, including measurements of concentrations of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} from
115 10,408 ground air monitors from 116 countries. GEOS Chem chemical transport model was used to
116 evaluate the sum of particulate sulfate, nitrate, ammonium, organic carbon, and the compositional
117 concentrations of mineral dust, combined with elevation and the distance to the nearest urban land
118 surface in a 0.1°×0.1° resolution (van Donkelaar et al. 2016). Satellite-based estimates of PM_{2.5} were
119 calculated based on the algorithms used in the GBD 2017 (van Donkelaar et al. 2016), with updated
120 satellite retrievals, chemical transport modelling, and ground-based monitoring at 0.1°×0.1° resolution.
121 Population data were obtained from the Gridded Population of the World (GPW) database, adjusted by
122 UN2015 Population Prospectus (GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators 2020). A Bayesian model was
123 then used to estimate the gridded concentrations, and Data Integration Model for Air Quality (DIMAQ)
124 was used to estimate ambient PM_{2.5} by matching the gridded estimates with the corresponding
125 coefficients from the calibration (Shaddick et al. 2018).

126

127 *2.3 COPD mortality and DALYs attributable to particulate matter pollution*

128 The GBD 2019 used the results of different types of studies that explored the association between
129 COPD and APM and HAP from solid fuels, and then used these results to fit the risk curve via meta-
130 regression Bayesian, regularized, trimmed (MR-BRT) splines. Theoretical minimum-risk exposure
131 level (TMREL) was incorporated to fit the risk curve beginning at null exposure (Turner et al. 2016),
132 which was defined as a uniform distribution given by the air pollution exposure distributions from
133 cohort studies conducted in North America (GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators 2020). In the GBD
134 2019, the lower and upper bounds of the distribution were 2.4 and 5.9 µg/m³. To calculate the
135 attributable burden due to APM and HAP, the GBD 2019 used the integrated exposure response (IER)
136 to obtain proportional population attributable fraction (PAF). In short, the COPD burden attributable to

137 APM or HAP was estimated by splitting the PAF attributable to PM at a country level based on the
138 average exposure levels.

139 We utilized age-and sex-specific mortality and DALYs to quantify the global burden of COPD
140 attributable to APM and HAP. Deaths due to COPD were estimated as the number of deaths in a
141 population over the specific study period, identified using the 9th and 10th International Classification of
142 Diseases and Injuries (ICD-9 and ICD-10). DALYs were calculated as the sum of YLLs and YLDs,
143 where YLLs were the number of years of life lost due to premature death under the GBD standard life
144 expectancy for each age group, and YLDs were the number of years lived with any short-term or long-
145 term health loss weighted by severity of the disability.

146 To further examine whether the disability or premature death contributed more to DALYs, we
147 calculated the proportion of YLLs in DALYs as follows:

148 *proportion of YLLs in DALYs = the number of YLLs ÷ the number of DALYs.*

149 We also estimated average YLLs per COPD death to assess the average life lost due to premature death
150 for COPD patients, using the following algorithm:

151 *the average YLLs per COPD death = the number of YLLs ÷ the number of deaths*

152

153 2.4 Statistical analysis

154 To control the impact of demographic differences, we used age-standardized mortality rate (ASMR)
155 and DALYs rate (ASDR). We then used percentage change and estimated annual percentage change
156 (EAPC) over 1990 to 2019 to estimate the temporal trends of ASMR and ASDR of COPD attributable
157 to PM air pollution (Liu et al. 2019). Age-standardized rate (ASR) was fitted in a regression model:

$$158 \ln(ASR) = \alpha + \beta x + \varepsilon$$

159 where x was the calendar year, and

$$160 EAPC = (\exp(\beta) - 1) * 100\%$$

161 The ASMR and ASDR would increase if the lower boundary of 95% confidence interval (CI) of
162 EAPC is higher than zero (Liu et al. 2019). In contrast, if the higher boundary of its 95% CI is lower
163 than zero, there is a decreasing trend for the ASMR and ASDR.

164 Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated between SDI and the ASMR and ASDR. A two-
165 sided P value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were performed

166 using R (version 3.6.1).

167

168 3. Results

169 3.1 Disease burden attributable to household air pollution from solid fuels

170 According to the GBD 2019, the COPD deaths attributable to HAP decreased by 57.28%, from
171 0.93 [95% uncertainty interval (UI): 0.59, 1.28] million in 1990 to 0.40 (95% UI: 0.24, 0.61) million in
172 2019 (Table S1). In 2019, the largest number of deaths was found in South Asia [0.23 (95% UI: 0.13,
173 0.35) million], accounting for 58.00% of the total COPD deaths attributable to HAP. Figure 1 presents
174 the global distribution of ASMR, ASDR, and their EAPC due to COPD attributable to HAP in 1990
175 and 2019. In 2019, the ASMR in Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands, and Nepal was highest,
176 exceeding 50 per 100,000 people. The ASMR from COPD attributable to HAP decreased by 80.88%
177 during 1990-2019, with an EAPC of -5.78% (95% CI: -5.98%, -5.57%), and the largest decreasing
178 EAPC in ASMR was found in High-income Asia Pacific [-10.29% (95% CI: -10.97%, -9.60%)]. Over
179 the study period, a clear declining trend was observed in global DALYs of COPD attributable to HAP
180 from 21.41 (95% UI: 13.75, 29.30) million in 1990 to 9.30 (95% UI: 5.69, 14.04) million in 2019
181 (Figure 1; Table S2), and the EAPC of ASDR was -5.48% (95% CI: -5.67%, -5.29%).

182

183 **Figure 1. The age-standardized rate of COPD mortality and DALYs attributable to household**
184 **particulate matter pollution from solid fuels by countries in 2019 and EAPC of ASMR and ASDR**
185 **from 1990 and 2019.** The unit for EAPC was %. ASDR, age-standardized DALYs rate; ASMR, age-
186 standardized mortality rate; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; DALYs, disability-adjusted
187 life-years; EAPC, estimated annual percentage change; HAP, household air pollution from solid fuels

188 The changes of YLLs-related indicators during 1990-2019 are presented in Table 1. A decreasing
 189 trend of the proportion of YLLs in DALYs due to COPD attributable to HAP was found over the past
 190 three decades. The proportion of YLLs in DALYs decreased by approximately 10.00% during 1990-
 191 2019 at global level, and ranged from 54.48% in High-income Asia Pacific to 88.68% in Oceania in
 192 2019 (Table 1).

193

194 **Table 1. The number of YLLs, proportion of YLLs in DALYs, and average YLLs per death due to**
 195 **COPD attributable to household particulate matter pollution from solid fuels in 1990 and 2019**

	Number of YLLs		Proportion of YLLs in DALYs		Average YLLs per death	
	Number× 10 ³		1990	2019	1990	2019
	1990	2019				
Global	18335.37	7175.21	85.65%	77.15%	19.66	18.01
Gender						
Male	9903.91	3787.21	88.46%	81.98%	20.67	18.89
Female	8431.45	3388.00	82.56%	72.38%	18.60	17.12
SDI quintile						
Low SDI	1980.05	1928.54	81.11%	75.37%	21.63	19.78
Low-middle SDI	6763.86	3913.89	84.72%	79.23%	20.74	18.11
Middle SDI	6918.40	1142.41	87.37%	74.69%	19.13	15.91
High-middle SDI	2635.26	183.25	87.39%	69.53%	17.44	14.60
High SDI	33.33	2.48	76.03%	65.67%	17.38	13.02
GBD region						
High-income Asia Pacific	0.94	0.10	62.78%	54.48%	15.85	11.24
Central Asia	51.66	11.78	82.75%	78.23%	20.61	20.62
East Asia	9644.79	1329.73	89.73%	78.92%	18.67	15.29
South Asia	6317.75	4233.46	82.81%	79.27%	20.96	18.32
Southeast Asia	943.65	470.77	79.84%	71.31%	20.40	18.63
Australasia	0.24	0.03	68.26%	61.53%	17.08	14.16
Caribbean	19.13	20.26	87.31%	85.67%	21.05	20.78

Oceania	39.12	62.36	90.36%	88.68%	23.98	23.31
Central Europe	63.79	12.03	79.45%	69.53%	18.55	16.51
Eastern Europe	35.32	3.17	80.68%	74.46%	19.40	17.87
Western Europe	5.44	0.80	71.87%	64.91%	14.93	11.51
High-income North America	0.65	0.38	61.44%	63.46%	17.45	15.93
Andean Latin America	13.72	6.15	82.52%	76.62%	17.59	14.54
Central Latin America	67.26	49.91	83.03%	82.35%	17.66	15.46
Southern Latin America	8.04	1.87	80.10%	76.09%	18.09	14.78
Tropical Latin America	120.02	29.52	84.71%	82.08%	19.10	16.68
North Africa and Middle East	159.42	72.09	79.00%	73.44%	21.74	22.84
Central Sub-Saharan Africa	123.81	152.50	78.40%	72.16%	22.70	21.26
Eastern Sub-Saharan Africa	388.50	397.59	77.05%	69.41%	22.41	21.10
Southern Sub-Saharan Africa	39.46	21.11	64.80%	61.50%	19.27	19.49
Western Sub-Saharan Africa	292.67	299.58	70.90%	65.31%	21.25	21.38

196 Abbreviations: COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; DALYs: disability-adjusted life-years; GBD: Global Burden of
197 Diseases Study; SDI: socio-demographic index; YLLs: years of life lost.

198

199 The average YLLs per COPD death attributable to HAP also decreased globally from 19.66 years
200 in 1990 to 18.01 years in 2019 (Table 1). However, it increased in four regions, including North Africa
201 and Middle East, Western Sub-Saharan Africa, Central Asia, and Southern Sub-Saharan Africa. The
202 highest average YLLs per COPD death in 2019 was seen in Oceania (23.31 years), and the lowest in
203 High-income Asia Pacific (11.24 years).

204

205 *3.2 Disease burden of COPD attributable to ambient particulate matter pollution*

206 In contrast to COPD deaths attributable to HAP, the COPD deaths attributable to APM increased by
207 97.61%, from 0.35 [95% *UI*: 0.22, 0.51] million people in 1990 to 0.70 (95% *UI*: 0.55, 0.86) million
208 people in 2019 (Table S3). And the global DALYs due to COPD attributable to APM increased by
209 93.11%, from 7.98 (95% *UI*: 5.06, 11.67) million in 1990 to 15.41 (95% *UI*: 12.39, 18.97) million in
210 2019. However, the global ASMR and ASDR declined, and the EAPCs of ASMR and ASDR during

211 1990-2019 were -0.58% (95% CI: -0.72%, -0.44%) and -0.40% (95% CI: -0.51%, -0.29%),
 212 respectively (Table S4). Figure 2 shows the global distribution of ASMR, ASDR and their EAPC due to
 213 COPD attributable to APM in 1990 and 2019.

214
 215 **Figure 2. The age-standardized rate of COPD mortality and DALYs attributable to ambient**
 216 **particulate matter pollution by countries in 2019 and EAPC of ASMR and ASDR from 1990 to**
 217 **2019.** The unit for EAPC was %. ASDR, age-standardized DALYs rate; ASMR, age-standardized
 218 mortality rate; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; DALYs, disability-adjusted life-years;
 219 EAPC, estimated annual percentage change; APM, ambient particulate matter pollution.

220
 221 The proportion of YLLs in DALYs due to COPD attributable to APM decreased across the world
 222 except in Caribbean and High-income North America, similar to that of HAP (Table 2). However, the
 223 proportion of YLLs in DALYs (75.96%) was still much higher than that of YLDs in DALYs (24.04%)
 224 in 2019. In 2019, the greatest proportion of YLLs in DALYs was observed in Oceania, and the smallest
 225 in high-income Asia Pacific.

226
 227 **Table 2. The number of YLLs, proportion of YLLs in DALYs, and average YLLs per death due to**
 228 **COPD attributable to ambient particulate matter pollution in 1990 and 2019**

Number of YLLs		Proportion of YLLs in DALYs		Average YLLs per death	
Number× 10 ³					
1990	2019	1990	2019	1990	2019

Global	6710.77	11708.53	84.07%	75.96%	19.08	16.85
Gender						
Male	4222.49	7253.28	86.78%	80.47%	20.02	17.62
Female	2488.28	4455.25	79.83%	69.61%	17.68	15.72
SDI quintile						
Low SDI	287.95	1017.38	82.64%	78.10%	21.41	19.13
Low-middle SDI	1267.55	4368.10	85.61%	80.88%	20.94	18.33
Middle SDI	2724.27	4195.93	86.42%	74.94%	19.50	16.30
High-middle SDI	1968.25	1724.52	84.98%	70.09%	17.88	14.60
High SDI	461.68	400.46	67.55%	61.84%	16.53	14.30
GBD region						
High-income Asia Pacific	38.43	63.08	60.24%	53.28%	15.77	11.84
Central Asia	46.12	57.09	82.62%	78.90%	20.95	20.56
East Asia	3611.58	4013.85	89.66%	77.28%	18.53	14.84
South Asia	1533.88	5669.80	82.65%	78.15%	21.14	18.43
Southeast Asia	252.05	452.15	78.17%	70.35%	20.51	18.63
Australasia	4.34	4.15	70.13%	62.29%	17.03	14.04
Caribbean	6.82	17.64	78.99%	79.09%	18.16	17.51
Oceania	2.48	6.88	90.54%	88.96%	23.69	23.09
Central Europe	132.22	85.95	78.80%	68.87%	18.94	16.71
Eastern Europe	234.40	75.27	82.05%	75.60%	19.64	18.21
Western Europe	291.70	186.09	71.32%	63.81%	15.48	12.89
High-income North America	142.15	116.42	60.08%	62.31%	17.55	15.73
Andean Latin America	9.59	18.47	83.08%	75.31%	17.55	14.03
Central Latin America	59.69	129.87	82.82%	80.58%	17.30	14.88
Southern Latin America	20.89	33.32	80.98%	76.81%	18.43	15.04
Tropical Latin America	59.55	88.50	86.23%	82.37%	19.83	17.00
North Africa and Middle East	165.12	408.70	74.26%	64.77%	21.08	19.73
Central Sub-Saharan Africa	12.32	37.46	79.59%	71.04%	22.64	21.50

Eastern Sub-Saharan Africa	20.46	62.28	77.73%	69.76%	22.11	20.99
Southern Sub-Saharan Africa	25.63	48.63	67.14%	64.53%	20.04	19.48
Western Sub-Saharan Africa	41.36	132.93	70.02%	64.29%	20.79	20.57

229 Abbreviations: COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; DALYs: disability-adjusted life-years; GBD: Global Burden
 230 of Diseases Study; SDI: socio-demographic index; YLLs: years of life lost.

231
 232 The global average YLLs per COPD death attributable to APM was 19.08 years in 1990, and
 233 declined to 16.85 years in 2019 (Table 2). Among different regions, Oceania had the highest average
 234 YLLs per COPD death (23.09 years) in 2019. Other regions with average YLLs per COPD death
 235 exceeding 20 years in 2019 included Central Asia, Western Sub-Saharan Africa, Eastern Sub-Saharan
 236 Africa, and Central Sub-Saharan Africa. The lowest average YLLs per COPD death in 2019 was
 237 observed in High-income Asia Pacific (11.84 years).

238

239 *3.3 Comparison on COPD burden attributable to HAP and APM*

240 The contribution of APM and HAP to global COPD burden has changed over the past three decades. In
 241 1990, HAP was the leading risk factor for COPD. The deaths and DALYs due to COPD attributable to
 242 HAP declined since 1990, and reached the similar level of those attributable to APM in 2010 (Figure
 243 3). APM became the second leading risk factor of COPD in 2019. The opposite phenomenon was
 244 observed in low-SDI region, in which the ASMR and ASDR due to COPD attributable to HAP were
 245 higher than those attributable to APM (Figure S2).

246

247 **Figure 3. Total numbers and age-standardized rates of COPD burden attributable to HAP and**

248 **APM from 1990 to 2019.** APM: ambient particulate matter pollution; COPD, chronic obstructive

249 pulmonary disease; DALYs, disability-adjusted life-years; HAP: household air pollution form solid

250 fuels; YLLs, years of life lost; YLDs, years lived with disability

251

252 The sex-specific and age-specific COPD burden was similar between those attributable to APM

253 and HAP (Figure S3; Figure 4). The global ASR of COPD deaths and DALYs were higher in males

254 than in females, and increased with age in 2019. The ASMR and ASDR of COPD in both males and
 255 females had declined, with a greater EAPC in males (Table S1; Table S2; Table S3; Table S4).
 256 Consequently, the between-sex disparity was narrowed. By contrast to mortality rate and DALYs rate
 257 due to COPD attributable to HAP decreasing in all age groups, the mortality rate and DALYs rate from
 258 COPD attributable to APM among people younger than 80 years decreased from 1990 to 2019, but
 259 increased among people elder than 80 years (Figure S4).

260
 261 **Figure 4. The age-standardized rates of deaths and DALYs due to global COPD attributable to**
 262 **household air pollution from solid fuels (A) and ambient particulate matter pollution (B) in 2019**
 263 **by sex and age.** COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; DALYs, disability-adjusted life-years

264
 265 Figure 5 shows that the ASMR and ASDR of COPD attributable to HAP decreased in all different
 266 SDI regions from 1990 to 2019. A greater decline was observed in regions with lower SDI, and the
 267 disparity among regions in ASR due to COPD attributable to HAP narrowed over the past 30 years.
 268 Compared with the ASMR and ASDR due to COPD attributable to HAP, those attributable to APM
 269 decreased in the middle SDI region, high-middle SDI region, and high SDI region, but increased in low
 270 and low-middle SDI regions (Figure 5). Furthermore, the greatest number of deaths [0.26 (95% UI:
 271 0.20, 0.32) million] was observed in the middle SDI region in 2019, accounting for 37.03% of the total
 272 number of global COPD deaths attributable to APM (Table S4). The correlation between SDI and

273 ASMR or ASDR was negative in both those attributable to APM and HAP (ASDR attributable to APM:
 274 $r = -0.28, p < 0.001$; ASDR attributable to HAP: $r = -0.70, p < 0.001$; Figure S5).

275
 276 **Figure 5. The age-standardized rates of COPD mortality and DALYs attributable to household**
 277 **air pollution from solid fuels (A) and ambient particulate matter pollution (B) from 1990 to 2019**
 278 **by socio-demographic index region. COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; SDI, socio-**
 279 **demographic index**

281 4. Discussion

282 To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to estimate the global spatial and temporal trends of
 283 mortality and DALYs due to COPD attributable to both HAP and APM from 1990 to 2019, and
 284 compare the differences between the two risk factors using a comprehensive approach. Notably, we
 285 found a clear decreasing trend in COPD mortality and DALYs attributable to HAP from solid fuels,
 286 whereas an increasing trend was observed for APM. APM overtook HAP to become the leading risk
 287 factor for COPD in 2019.

288 Several previous studies have explored the potential burden of disease attributable to PM air
289 pollution, but only at a national level (Bennett et al. 2019, Chen et al. 2017, Khomenko et al. 2021).
290 For example, one national study from the United States found that approximately 130 thousand deaths
291 due to cardiorespiratory diseases, including COPD, were estimated attributable to PM_{2.5} pollution
292 during 1999-2015 (Bennett et al. 2019). Another study conducted in China showed that 250 thousand
293 COPD deaths were attributable to PM_{2.5} in 2017 (Liu et al. 2021). However, most of these studies have
294 focused on the outcome of all-cause mortality, and few studies assessed the COPD burden from a
295 global perspective. In this study, using the latest data of the GBD 2019, we mainly focused on the
296 COPD burden attributable to both APM and HAP from solid fuels exposure. The COPD burden
297 attributable to PM pollution in 2017 estimated in the GBD 2019 was slightly higher than in GBD 2017.
298 These differences might be due to the newly added data, updated PM exposure assessment, and the
299 changes in the exposure-risk curve (GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators 2020).

300 The substantial reduction in COPD mortality and DALYs attributable to HAP observed in our
301 study might have benefited from global efforts on mitigation of household PM air pollution (Watts et
302 al. 2018). Universal access to affordable and clean energy is one of the United Nations Sustainable
303 Development Goals, and government interventions have led to achievements in promoting clean
304 energy, especially in Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa (IEA et al. 2019). For example, the Chinese
305 government had implemented a series of measures to reduce HAP, such as China's National Improved
306 Stove Program and the Air Pollution Prevention and Control Action Plan (Edwards et al. 2007, Huang
307 et al. 2018), which were aimed to reduce air pollution emission by optimizing the industrial
308 infrastructure, increasing clean energy application and so on. Some studies reported that such transition
309 in household fuels has resulted in a reduction in household PM_{2.5} exposure and HAP-associated burden
310 of diseases (Pope et al. 2017, Quansah et al. 2017, Thakur et al. 2018). Previous measurements were
311 imperative to reduce the HAP-related COPD burden. However, around three billion people globally
312 still rely on solid fuels for cooking and heating (IEA et al. 2019).

313 Comparatively, the number of COPD deaths and DALYs attributable to APM increased
314 worldwide during 1990-2019. This change was probably due to population growth, population aging,
315 and the increase of ambient PM pollution exposure in regions with lower SDI (GBD 2019 Risk Factors
316 Collaborators 2020). After adjusting for population growth and age structure, the global age-

317 standardized rate of mortality and DALYs for COPD decreased slightly. However, over 90% of the
318 world population still lives in areas with APM exceeding the WHO limits (World Health Organization
319 (WHO) 2021), and APM still remains a challenge to global public health.

320 Interestingly, we found that the proportion of YLLs in DALYs due to COPD attributable to APM
321 and HAP decreased from 1990 to 2019, which might be due to the improvement of COPD treatment,
322 such as better control of COPD risk factors, advanced pharmacotherapy, and other interventions (Rabe
323 & Watz 2017). Similarly, a decreasing trend of the average YLLs per COPD death attributable to APM
324 and HAP was observed. However, the average loss of life due to COPD premature death attributable to
325 APM and HAP in 2019 was still as high as 16.85 years and 18.01 years, respectively, which were close
326 to 23% and 25% of global life expectancy (World Health Organization (WHO) 2020). Given the high
327 average YLL per death, more attention should be allocated to COPD amelioration efforts.

328 In 2019, considerable regional differences in the age-standardized mortality rate and DALYs of
329 COPD attributable to HAP and APM were observed. These differences could be attributable to multiple
330 factors, such as the geographical differences in the composition of the PM and the influence of SDI.
331 Differences in chemical compositions with different toxicity might result in different health impacts
332 (Yang et al. 2019). Moreover, the correlation analysis in this study revealed a negative correlation
333 between SDI and the ASMR of COPD attributable to HAP and APM. The finding is consistent with
334 previous studies (Liu et al. 2008, Siddharthan et al. 2018), suggesting the development inequalities
335 across different SDI regions may affect the impact of PM on COPD death and DALYs. As low and
336 middle income countries mainly rely on traditional energy sources for household cooking and heating,
337 HAP exposure levels are much higher in these countries than in high-income countries (Gordon et al.
338 2014). In addition, the lack of high-quality public health care in low-income countries due to economic
339 deprivation and the relatively poor health awareness of the population may amplify COPD burden due
340 to PM pollution (Bazargani et al. 2014, GBD 2019 Demographics Collaborators 2020). Interestingly,
341 the largest mortality and DALYs attributable to APM were observed in middle-SDI region, which was
342 possibly due to the rapid industrialization in these countries driven by massive energy consumption and
343 power generation (GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators 2020). On the other hand, a series of air
344 quality control measures were conducted in the study period in countries with higher SDI, such as
345 coordinated policies and other interventions on industries and vehicles, which promoted the reduction

346 of APM in these regions (Burns et al. 2020).

347 Given the increasing trend in COPD burden attributable to APM observed in our study, continued
348 efforts are needed to mitigate ambient air pollution to reduce COPD disease burden, especially in more
349 developed regions (i.e., regions with middle and high SDI). As for low-SDI regions, HAP still remains
350 an important risk factor to COPD and effective measures targeting household air pollution are needed,
351 such as the promotion of the transitions from solid fuels to clean energy.

352 In subgroup analyses, we found higher age-standardized mortality and DALYs of COPD
353 attributable to PM in males than in females, except for DALYs attributable to HAP in Oceania and
354 Central Sub-Saharan Africa. Such sex disparity, especially those attributable to HAP, might seem to be
355 unplausible, which could be partially due to the improvement in household energy consumption, the
356 differences in risk behaviors related to COPD and the higher number of COPD mortality in males
357 (GBD Chronic Respiratory Disease Collaborators 2020, IEA et al. 2019). Males had greater prevalence
358 of some other risk factors of COPD (GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators 2020, GBD Chronic
359 Respiratory Disease Collaborators 2020), such as smoking and occupational dust exposure, which
360 might influence the effect of PM air pollution on COPD burden. For example, both epidemiological
361 and animal studies have found that the joint effect of smoking and particulate matter on COPD was
362 more pronounced than their separate effects (Su et al. 2021, Wang et al. 2019). However, the
363 underlying mechanisms remain unknown and more studies are needed to illuminate this sex difference.

364 Although APM and HAP are mainly composed of air-suspended particles, the sources of them are
365 different. In the GBD 2019, HAP mainly originated from the combustion of solid fuels, in contrast to
366 APM which had more different types of sources, such as traffic pollution and industrial pollution (GBD
367 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators 2020, Zhang et al. 2019). These different sources for APM and HAP
368 may result in different compositions, leading to different toxic effects on cardiopulmonary function
369 (Wu et al. 2014, Zhou et al. 2021). For example, one study found that HAP was associated with a
370 decrement in forced expiratory volume in first second (FEV1), while APM was associated with a
371 reduction in peak expiratory flow (PEF) (Chi et al. 2019). Other studies also reported that PM from
372 different constituents and sources had different cardiopulmonary effects (Wu et al. 2016, Zhang et al.
373 2021).

374 Our study has some limitations. First, the estimates in the GBD 2019 depended on the availability

375 and quality of the primary data in each country or territory with inevitable variations (GBD 2019
376 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators 2020, Li et al. 2020). Second, misdiagnosis and underdiagnosis due
377 to lack of adequate equipment might lead to underestimation of COPD burden attributable to PM
378 pollution (Li et al. 2020). Third, HAP can originate from various sources other than solid fuel
379 combustion, such as tobacco smoke, furnishing and construction materials (Ni et al. 2020), whereas
380 HAP exposure in the GBD study was estimated only based on the consumption of solid fuels (GBD
381 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators 2020). This might have led to an underestimation of the COPD burden
382 attributable to HAP. Fourth, there is possible residual confounding due to unmeasured or unknown
383 confounding factors in these studies included in the GBD 2019, which could have affected the
384 assessment of the risk curves. Finally, the GBD 2019 did not take into account PM components, though
385 studies have shown that different PM components have different health effects (Yang et al. 2019).
386 These limitations increase the uncertainty of the results, and therefore more studies on HAP and
387 COPD, as well as the component of PM and COPD, are needed in the future.

388

389 **5. Conclusions**

390 In conclusion, we found that the number of mortality and DALYs for COPD attributable to HAP
391 decreased markedly over the past three decades, while those attributable to APM increased.
392 Geographical differences were observed as the global COPD burden attributable to APM in 2019 was
393 higher than those due to HAP in high- and middle- SDI regions, whereas in low-SDI regions, HAP was
394 still a major contributor. More effective control measures should be implemented to reduce COPD
395 burden associated with APM pollution, while improvement of household clean energy is still needed to
396 reduce household air pollution in low-SDI countries.

397

398 **Data availability**

399 Data sources are available in the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019.

400 (<http://ghdx.healthdata.org/gbd-results-tool>)

401

402

403 **References**

404 Bazargani Y T, de Boer A, Leufkens H G, Mantel-Teeuwisse A K (2014): Essential medicines for COPD

405 and asthma in low and middle-income countries. *Thorax* 69, 1149-51

406 Bennett J E, Tamura-Wicks H, Parks R M, Burnett R T, Pope C A, 3rd, Bechle M J, Marshall J D, Danaei
407 G, Ezzati M (2019): Particulate matter air pollution and national and county life expectancy loss
408 in the USA: A spatiotemporal analysis. *PLoS Med* 16, e1002856

409 Burns J, Boogaard H, Polus S, Pfadenhauer L M, Rohwer A C, van Erp A M, Turley R, Rehfuss E A
410 (2020): Interventions to reduce ambient air pollution and their effects on health: An abridged
411 Cochrane systematic review. *Environ Int* 135, 105400

412 Cao D, Li D, Wu Y, Qian Z, Liu Y, Liu Q, Sun J, Guo Y, Zhang S, Jiao G, Yang X, Wang C, McMillin S
413 E, Zhang X, Lin H (2021): Ambient PM_{2.5} exposure and hospital cost and length of hospital stay
414 for respiratory diseases in 11 cities in Shanxi Province, China. *Thorax* 76, 815–820.
415 doi:10.1136/thoraxjnl-2020-215838

416 Chen R, Yin P, Meng X, Liu C, Wang L, Xu X, Ross J A, Tse L A, Zhao Z, Kan H, Zhou M (2017): Fine
417 Particulate Air Pollution and Daily Mortality. A Nationwide Analysis in 272 Chinese Cities. *Am*
418 *J Respir Crit Care Med* 196, 73-81

419 Chi R, Chen C, Li H, Pan L, Zhao B, Deng F, Guo X (2019): Different health effects of indoor- and
420 outdoor-originated PM_{2.5} on cardiopulmonary function in COPD patients and healthy elderly
421 adults. *Indoor Air* 29, 192-201

422 Edwards R D, Liu Y, He G, Yin Z, Sinton J, Peabody J, Smith K R (2007): Household CO and PM
423 measured as part of a review of China's National Improved Stove Program. *Indoor Air* 17, 189-
424 203

425 GBD 2019 Demographics Collaborators (2020): Global age-sex-specific fertility, mortality, healthy life
426 expectancy (HALE), and population estimates in 204 countries and territories, 1950-2019: a
427 comprehensive demographic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *Lancet* 396,
428 1160-1203

429 GBD 2019 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators (2020): Global burden of 369 diseases and injuries in 204
430 countries and territories, 1990-2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease
431 Study 2019. *Lancet* 396, 1204-1222

432 GBD 2019 Risk Factors Collaborators (2020): Global burden of 87 risk factors in 204 countries and
433 territories, 1990-2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019.
434 *Lancet* 396, 1223-1249

435 GBD Chronic Respiratory Disease Collaborators (2020): Prevalence and attributable health burden of
436 chronic respiratory diseases, 1990-2017: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease
437 Study 2017. *Lancet Respir Med* 8, 585-596

438 Gordon S B et al. (2014): Respiratory risks from household air pollution in low and middle income
439 countries. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine* 2, 823-860

440 Huang J, Pan X, Guo X, Li G (2018): Health impact of China's Air Pollution Prevention and Control
441 Action Plan: an analysis of national air quality monitoring and mortality data. *Lancet Planet*
442 *Health* 2, e313-e323

443 IEA, IRENA, UNSD, WB, WHO (2019): Tracking SDG 7: The Energy Progress Report 2019,
444 Washington DC. <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/energy/>. Accessed 05 April 2021

445 Khomenko S, Cirach M, Pereira-Barboza E, Mueller N, Barrera-Gómez J, Rojas-Rueda D, de Hoogh K,
446 Hoek G, Nieuwenhuijsen M (2021): Premature mortality due to air pollution in European cities:
447 a health impact assessment. *The Lancet Planetary Health* 5, e121-e134

448 Li M H, Fan L C, Mao B, Yang J W, Choi A M K, Cao W J, Xu J F (2016): Short-term Exposure to

449 Ambient Fine Particulate Matter Increases Hospitalizations and Mortality in COPD: A
450 Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Chest* 149, 447-458

451 Li X, Cao X, Guo M, Xie M, Liu X (2020): Trends and risk factors of mortality and disability adjusted
452 life years for chronic respiratory diseases from 1990 to 2017: systematic analysis for the Global
453 Burden of Disease Study 2017. *BMJ* 368, m234

454 Liu M, Saari R K, Zhou G, Li J, Han L, Liu X (2021): Recent trends in premature mortality and health
455 disparities attributable to ambient PM_{2.5} exposure in China: 2005-2017. *Environ Pollut* 279,
456 116882

457 Liu S, Zhou Y, Liu S, Chen X, Zou W, Zhao D, Li X, Pu J, Huang L, Chen J, Li B, Liu S, Ran P (2017):
458 Association between exposure to ambient particulate matter and chronic obstructive pulmonary
459 disease: results from a cross-sectional study in China. *Thorax* 72, 788-795

460 Liu Y, Lee K, Perez-Padilla R, Hudson N L, Mannino D M (2008): Outdoor and indoor air pollution and
461 COPD-related diseases in high- and low-income countries. *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis* 12, 115-27

462 Liu Z, Jiang Y, Yuan H, Fang Q, Cai N, Suo C, Jin L, Zhang T, Chen X (2019): The trends in incidence
463 of primary liver cancer caused by specific etiologies: Results from the Global Burden of Disease
464 Study 2016 and implications for liver cancer prevention. *J Hepatol* 70, 674-683

465 Ni Y, Shi G, Qu J (2020): Indoor PM_{2.5}, tobacco smoking and chronic lung diseases: A narrative review.
466 *Environ Res* 181, 108910

467 Niu X, Jones T, BeruBe K, Chuang H C, Sun J, Ho K F (2021): The oxidative capacity of indoor source
468 combustion derived particulate matter and resulting respiratory toxicity. *Sci Total Environ* 767,
469 144391

470 Park J, Kim H J, Lee C H, Lee C H, Lee H W (2021): Impact of long-term exposure to ambient air
471 pollution on the incidence of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: A systematic review and
472 meta-analysis. *Environ Res* 194, 110703

473 Pope D, Bruce N, Dherani M, Jagoe K, Rehfuess E (2017): Real-life effectiveness of 'improved' stoves
474 and clean fuels in reducing PM_{2.5} and CO: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Environ Int*
475 101, 7-18

476 Quansah R, Semple S, Ochieng C A, Juvekar S, Armah F A, Luginaah I, Emina J (2017): Effectiveness
477 of interventions to reduce household air pollution and/or improve health in homes using solid
478 fuel in low-and-middle income countries: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Environ Int*
479 103, 73-90

480 Rabe K F, Watz H (2017): Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *The Lancet* 389, 1931-1940

481 Sadhra S S, Mohammed N, Kurmi O P, Fishwick D, De Matteis S, Hutchings S, Jarvis D, Ayres J G,
482 Rushton L (2020): Occupational exposure to inhaled pollutants and risk of airflow obstruction:
483 a large UK population-based UK Biobank cohort. *Thorax* 75, 468-475

484 Shaddick G, Thomas M L, Green A, Brauer M, van Donkelaar A, Burnett R, Chang H H, Cohen A, Van
485 Dingenen R, Dora C, Gumy S, Liu Y, Martin R, Waller L A, West J, Zidek J V, Pruss-Ustun A
486 (2018): Data integration model for air quality: a hierarchical approach to the global estimation
487 of exposures to ambient air pollution. *J R Stat Soc C-Appl* 67, 231-253

488 Shupler M, Balakrishnan K, Ghosh S, Thangavel G, Stroud-Drinkwater S, Adair-Rohani H, Lewis J,
489 Mehta S, Brauer M (2018a): Global household air pollution database: Kitchen concentrations
490 and personal exposures of particulate matter and carbon monoxide. *Data Brief* 21, 1292-1295

491 Shupler M, Godwin W, Frostad J, Gustafson P, Arku R E, Brauer M (2018b): Global estimation of
492 exposure to fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) from household air pollution. *Environ Int* 120, 354-

493 363

494 Siddharthan T, Grigsby M R, Goodman D, Chowdhury M, Rubinstein A, Irazola V, Gutierrez L, Miranda
495 J J, Bernabe-Ortiz A, Alam D, Kirenga B, Jones R, van Gemert F, Wise R A, Checkley W (2018):
496 Association between Household Air Pollution Exposure and Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary
497 Disease Outcomes in 13 Low- and Middle-Income Country Settings. *Am J Respir Crit Care*
498 *Med* 197, 611-620

499 Singanayagam A, Johnston S L (2020): Long-term impact of inhaled corticosteroid use in asthma and
500 chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD): Review of mechanisms that underlie risks.
501 *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology* 146, 1292-1294

502 Su J, Ye Q, Zhang D, Zhou J, Tao R, Ding Z, Lu G, Liu J, Xu F (2021): Joint association of cigarette
503 smoking and PM_{2.5} with COPD among urban and rural adults in regional China. *BMC Pulm*
504 *Med* 21, 87

505 Thakur M, Nuyts P A W, Boudewijns E A, Flores Kim J, Faber T, Babu G R, van Schayck O C P, Been
506 J V (2018): Impact of improved cookstoves on women's and child health in low and middle
507 income countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Thorax* 73, 1026-1040

508 Tian F, Qi J, Wang L, Yin P, Qian Z, Ruan Z, Liu J, Liu Y, McMillin S E, Wang C, Lin H, Zhou M (2020):
509 Differentiating the effects of ambient fine and coarse particles on mortality from
510 cardiopulmonary diseases: A nationwide multicity study. *Environment International* 145,
511 106096

512 Turner M C, Jerrett M, Pope C A, 3rd, Krewski D, Gapstur S M, Diver W R, Beckerman B S, Marshall
513 J D, Su J, Crouse D L, Burnett R T (2016): Long-Term Ozone Exposure and Mortality in a
514 Large Prospective Study. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 193, 1134-42

515 van Donkelaar A, Martin R V, Brauer M, Hsu N C, Kahn R A, Levy R C, Lyapustin A, Sayer A M, Winker
516 D M (2016): Global Estimates of Fine Particulate Matter using a Combined Geophysical-
517 Statistical Method with Information from Satellites, Models, and Monitors. *Environ Sci Technol*
518 50, 3762-72

519 Wang Z, Zhao J, Wang T, Du X, Xie J (2019): Fine-particulate matter aggravates cigarette smoke extract-
520 induced airway inflammation via Wnt5a-ERK pathway in COPD. *Int J Chron Obstruct Pulmon*
521 *Dis* 14, 979-994

522 Watts N et al. (2018): The Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: from 25 years of inaction to
523 a global transformation for public health. *Lancet* 391, 581-630

524 World Health Organization (WHO) (2020): GHE: Life expectancy and healthy life expectancy.
525 [https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/mortality-and-global-health-estimates/ghe-life-
526 expectancy-and-healthy-life-expectancy](https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/mortality-and-global-health-estimates/ghe-life-expectancy-and-healthy-life-expectancy). Accessed 28 April 2021

527 World Health Organization (WHO) (2021): Air pollution. [https://www.who.int/health-topics/air-
528 pollution#tab=tab_2](https://www.who.int/health-topics/air-pollution#tab=tab_2). Accessed 25 April 2021

529 Wu S, Deng F, Wei H, Huang J, Wang X, Hao Y, Zheng C, Qin Y, Lv H, Shima M, Guo X (2014):
530 Association of cardiopulmonary health effects with source-appointed ambient fine particulate
531 in Beijing, China: a combined analysis from the Healthy Volunteer Natural Relocation (HVNR)
532 study. *Environ Sci Technol* 48, 3438-48

533 Wu S, Yang D, Pan L, Shan J, Li H, Wei H, Wang B, Huang J, Baccarelli A A, Shima M, Deng F, Guo X
534 (2016): Chemical constituents and sources of ambient particulate air pollution and biomarkers
535 of endothelial function in a panel of healthy adults in Beijing, China. *Sci Total Environ* 560-
536 561, 141-9

537 Xia X, Qiu H, Kwok T, Ko F W S, Man C L, Ho K-F (2020): Time course of blood oxygen saturation
538 responding to short-term fine particulate matter among elderly healthy subjects and patients
539 with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *The Science of the total environment* 723, 138022
540 Yang Y, Ruan Z, Wang X, Yang Y, Mason T G, Lin H, Tian L (2019): Short-term and long-term exposures
541 to fine particulate matter constituents and health: A systematic review and meta-analysis.
542 *Environ Pollut* 247, 874-882
543 Zhang J, Liu W, Xu Y, Cai C, Liu Y, Tao S, Liu W (2019): Distribution characteristics of and personal
544 exposure with polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and particulate matter in indoor and outdoor
545 air of rural households in Northern China. *Environ Pollut* 255, 113176
546 Zhang W, Li H, Pan L, Xu J, Yang X, Dong W, Shan J, Wu S, Deng F, Chen Y, Guo X (2021): Chemical
547 constituents and sources of indoor PM_{2.5} and cardiopulmonary function in patients with chronic
548 obstructive pulmonary disease: Estimation of individual and joint effects. *Environ Res* 197,
549 111191
550 Zhou L, Tao Y, Li H, Niu Y, Li L, Kan H, Xie J, Chen R (2021): Acute effects of fine particulate matter
551 constituents on cardiopulmonary function in a panel of COPD patients. *Sci Total Environ* 770,
552 144753
553
554

555 **Figure legends:**

556

557

558 **Figure 3. Total numbers and age-standardized rates of COPD burden attributable to HAP and**
559 **APM from 1990 to 2019.**

560 Abbreviations: COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; DALYs: disability-adjusted life-years;

561 YLLs: years of life lost; YLDs: years lived with disability.

562

563 **Figure 4. Age-standardized rates of deaths and DALYs due to global COPD attributable to**
564 **household air pollution from solid fuels (A) and ambient particulate matter pollution (B) in**
565 **2019 by sex and age.**

566 Abbreviations: COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; DALYs, disability-adjusted life-

567 years.

568

569 **Figure 5. The age-standardized rates of COPD mortality and DALYs attributable to**
570 **household air pollution from solid fuels (A) and ambient particulate matter pollution (B) from**
571 **1990 to 2019 by socio-demographic index region.**

572 Abbreviations: COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; SDI, Socio-demographic Index.

573